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Can the localization ratio be considered as a resilience indicator in the supply chain?

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Abstract

Supply chain resilience is concerned with establishing disruption-resistant operational practices and ensuring the achievement of some planned performance responding to shocks. Thus, resilience is both a quality and a quantity. The existing literature is rich in analyzing each of these two parts separately. However, studies connecting quantity and quality perspectives are rare. We position our study in the context of debates about the impact of localization on supply chain resilience. We depart from some industrial practices that use a localization degree to measure resilience. Two substantial contributions emerge from this study. First, we define a localization index of manufacturing activities in the supply chain. Second, we test two hypotheses using a discrete-event simulation model in anyLogistix: (i) Does a localization ratio impact supply chain resilience, and (ii) what role does the severity of shocks play in the impact of localization on supply chain resilience? Our findings suggest that localization impacts supply chain resilience. A positive effect of localization can be observed in scenarios with short-term disruptions, and it decreases with an increase in shock duration and severity. A mixed strategy combining local and global footprints can be recommended as a resilient supply chain strategy.

Keywords: supply chain; resilience; ripple effect; simulation; performance

1. Introduction

Outsourcing and globalization of supply chains have been considered primary drivers of profitability and cost efficiency for a long time (Wan et al., 2019; Sawik, 2023b). Triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic and accelerated by geopolitical crises, the debate of outsourcing versus on-shoring (i.e., localization) of supply chains is on the agenda of industry and governmental institutions alike (Ivanov, 2025e). The extant literature has not reached a consensus yet. While some studies favor

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localization solutions because of shorter lead times and higher responsiveness, others counter-argue that a global footprint yields higher diversification and adaptability (Li et al., 2017; Alikhani et al., 2023; Gruchmann et al., 2024; Kim et al., 2024; Lee and Moon, 2024; Liu et al., 2024).

According to the McKinsey report by Aliche et al. (2024), regionalization and nearshoring belong to the main resilience measures, along with inventory buffers and dual sourcing. Consider two practical examples that motivate our study. Schneider Electric, ranked #1 in the Gartner Global Supply Chain Top 25 ranking in 2024, reorganized its supply chains through regionalization and localization, dual sourcing, building spare capacity in plants, and building R&D capability in semi-conductors and electronics. Using a multi-hub operating model, in 2021, 92% of Schneider's supplied goods came from the same region as its manufacturing sites, and 80% of Schneider's sales were produced in the same region as its customers (Schneider Electric, 2023). They have increased the number of locations where safety stock is held to improve resilience (Banker, 2024). AGCO Corporation, an agricultural equipment manufacturer, integrates lean and resilience by multiple sourcing, combining local/domestic sources and international suppliers. Their lean manufacturing system adds adaptability through assemble-to-order and postponement production strategies. Through the decentralized logistics networks, AGCO was capable of adapting its logistics in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, anticipating lockdowns (Banker, 2020).

Despite the increased interest in the trade-off of localization versus globalization, the literature lacks indicators to judge about advantages of nearshoring in the supply chain. In addition, we are not aware of any studies that inform decision-makers about stress testing methodologies when analyzing resilience in the context of localization versus global sourcing. To close these research gaps, our first objective is to define a new indicator—a localization ratio—and examine its informative value for resilience analysis. We consider the above-described practice of Schneider Electric, which measures the fraction of local supply and production in the overall volumes and relates it to resilience. Building on this practice, we define a localization ratio indicator and examine its sensitivity to different nature and severity disruption scenarios through discrete-event simulation in anyLogistix. Second, we propose a simulation-based method for stress testing supply chain resilience when comparing localization versus global sourcing. The simulations are performed relying on a well-established global supply chain model used in Ivanov (2020) for the COVID-19 pandemic analysis.

Our contribution is twofold. First, we develop an index to quantify the impact of supply chain localization on its resilience. Second, we deduce useful managerial insights into whether and when a localization ratio can be considered a resilience indicator in the supply chain. Our main insights are as follows. First, localization value for resilience depends on the type of risks and disruption scenarios considered. Localization might be helpful in case of short-term disruptions in combination with inventory buffers. For long-term crises such as a pandemic, localization is not the right resilience strategy. Second, localization and global sourcing are not a trade-off. They are supplementary strategies. Diversified sourcing and production flexibility allow the adaptation of the supply chain without additional investments and in a very short time. The primary advantage of localization in enhancing resilience is to reduce lead times and improve service levels by relocating suppliers and facilities closer to production and consumption points.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 analyzes the existing literature. In Section 3, we define our simulation model and the localization index. Section 4 is devoted to

experimental analysis. We conclude the paper in Section 5 by summarizing major insights and outlining future research directions.

2. Literature analysis

Supply chain resilience assessment and practices in the context of localization are in their infancy (Wan et al., 2019). However, there is a rich body of resilience literature dealing with supply chain resilience simulation and recovery, which is relevant to our study. We begin the analysis with this stream of literature and then detail it with the papers explicitly dealing with localization aspects.

Simulation has been successfully and increasingly used for modeling supply chain dynamics under disruptions (Macdonald et al., 2018; Stewart and Ivanov, 2022; Jackson et al., 2024). In particular, the focus was on discrete event simulation, agent-based modeling, and system dynamics (Llaguno et al., 2022; Ivanov, 2025c). Discrete event simulation has been extensively used in studies on supply chain resilience and stress testing (Moosavi and Hosseini, 2021; Singh et al., 2021; Dolgui et al., 2025; Ivanov, 2025d). Most of these studies have used anyLogistix software as a simulation environment (Stewart and Ivanov, 2022; Timperio et al., 2022). Literature provides strong evidence that anyLogistix can be successfully used for simulation, optimization, and performance visualization of supply chain performance and dynamic behaviors in stress testing, recovery, and resilience analyses motivating us to use this tool in our study.

While discrete-event simulation dominates the disruption analysis field, other methods such as agent-based modeling, system dynamics, and hybrid approaches should be mentioned as well (Moroni et al., 2025). Agent-based modeling allows to add behavioral components, competition, and individual adaptation rules (Backs et al., 2021; Rozhkov et al., 2022). System dynamics can help in deducing managerial insights related to system-wide effects and unintended consequences, which are difficult to define in rule-based discrete event models (Ghadge et al., 2022). Adaptive networks can exhibit higher resilience because they can accommodate dynamic changes in connectivity, that is, they exhibit structural dynamics (Demirel et al., 2019; Dolgui et al., 2024). Moreover, hybrid simulation is an approach that integrates discrete event simulation, agents, and system dynamics. This approach allows decision-makers to incorporate process, behavior, and systems models. However, Taghikhah et al. (2021) underline that the main challenges of hybrid simulation are difficulties in verification and validation, computational complexity, and insufficient practical applicability for solving real cases.

Turning to the localization context, Sawik (2023b) developed a scenario-based stochastic mixed integer programming model designed for risk-neutral and risk-averse optimization of supply chain reshoring to the domestic market. The model accounts for the ripple effect originating from disruptions in a foreign region and propagating throughout the supply chain. Reshoring decisions are evaluated for both tier-one parts suppliers and assembly plants, considering disruptions in supply, manufacturing, logistics, and demand across the entire network. Sawik's (2023b, 2025) studies offer frameworks integrating strategic supply chain reshoring with resilience assessment, in particular, lost sales. The results show that reshoring enhances the domestic supply chain's ability to meet market demand. Full reshoring improves baseline (business-as-usual) performance, while even partial reshoring helps mitigate the ripple effect's adverse impacts. However, in risk-averse scenarios, reshoring is avoided if it does not reduce worst-case costs, especially worst-case lost sales.

For measuring the impact of disruptions on supply chains, different approaches have been proposed for resilience quantification. A common way to judge about resilience in simulation studies is analysis of deviations in some performance indicators, for example, on-time delivery (OTD), fill rate (FR), annual sales and revenues (Ivanov, 2025b). Methods of network theory are used to measure supply chain resilience from positions of network connectivity. Degree and betweenness centrality, connectivity, and reachability coefficients have been used to quantify structural integrity, connectivity, and flexibility (Li and Zobel, 2020). Another research stream focuses on measuring the intensity of performance loss and recovery (Torabi et al., 2015; Zobel et al., 2021). Finally, time-related resilience measures exist. For example, Simchi-Levi et al. (2015) measured resilience using time-to-recover and time-to-survive. If time-to-survive is longer than time-to-recover, a supply chain is considered resilient. Mosayebi et al. (2024) analyzed time-to-adapt as the duration from the decision to adapt to the point when the new, modified process is operational.

In the context of our study, metrics related to operational and customer performance are of particular interest. Lost sales are one of the indicators frequently used in supply chain resilience assessment. In the literature, several indicators such as FR (for warehouses) and OTD (measured at customers) have been used to analyze resilience (Rozhkov, 2022; Sawik, 2023a; Sawik and Sawik, 2024). Singh et al. (2021) and Ivanov (2020) used OTD as a “ratio of on-time delivered orders to the total number of orders placed” to assess the performance impact of disruptions. Assuming that a disruption translates to late deliveries to customers, a reduction in OTD was associated with decreased resilience. Ivanov (2025a) demonstrates that while the OTD indicator facilitates the detection of a supply chain disruption from the customer’s perspective, FR enables the identification of a disruption from an operational perspective. Moreover, Ivanov (2025b) illustrates that FR is located closer to the disruption point, and so it is capable of alerting about disruptions in a faster fashion. OTD changes with time delays and can be influenced by additional factors, for example, inventory-in-transit (Wang et al., 2016; Li et al., 2022; Rozhkov, 2022).

FR and OTD analysis is dynamic, so discrete-event simulation has been widely adopted (Saisridhar et al., 2024). This method allows for assessing how a system responds to disruptions over time and comparing its performance under various disruption scenarios (Dolgui et al., 2020; Ivanov, 2020a; Moosavi and Hosseini, 2021). Ivanov, 2017, Dolgui et al. (2020) employed anyLogistix to analyze the interrelations between the ripple effect and bullwhip effects, visualizing their dynamics and performance impact. Burgos and Ivanov (2021) assessed the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on a European food retail supply chain. Further studies by Ivanov (2020), Singh et al. (2021), and Schleifenheimer and Ivanov (2024) leveraged anyLogistix to predict the pandemic’s impact on supply chain dynamics and performance. These studies contextualized pandemics as a distinct type of supply chain risk characterized by long-term disruptions, unpredictable scaling, and uncertain recovery timelines.

Moosavi and Hosseini (2021) examined supply chain resilience during COVID-19, incorporating recovery strategies into their analysis. Timperio et al. (2022) developed a decision-support framework for humanitarian logistics using anyLogistix, optimizing both network structures and operational control policies. Ivanov (2024b) investigated the impact of financial disruptions on supply chain resilience using discrete-event simulation in anyLogistix.

3. Simulation model and localization ratio

3.1. Localization ratio

Our idea of the localization index (1) is guided by the Schneider Electric case (Schneider Electric, 2023), which analyzes a ratio of regional production to total sales as a resilience metric. We propose the following localization index (Equation 1).

$$\text{Localization index (LI)} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\text{manufacturing in the region of sales}}{\text{total sales}} * 100\%. \quad (1)$$

We illustrate the localization index LI using a simple example. Consider five regions of sales, each with a sales volume of 20 units. For example, one factory in one of these regions produces products that generate total sales of 100 units across all markets, including the one where the factory is located. In this case, $LI = 0.2$ since only one market is supplied locally: $LI = 20/100 + 0/100 + 0/100 + 0/100 + 0/100 = 0.2 * 100\% = 20\%$ localization ratio. If we would have three factories, for example, one producing 70 units in region A for all regions, the second one, 15 units in region D for region D, and the third one, 15 units in region E for region E, then $LI = 20/100 + 0/100 + 0/100 + 15/100 + 15/100 = 0.5 * 100\% = 50\%$ localization ratio.

Note that the proposed index accounts for the size of a region in terms of sales volume. Boundaries between regions would be defined in practice based on organizational structure of a firm, for example, regional sales networks.

3.2. Use case

We model a global supply chain of a company producing and selling five different products based on Ivanov (2020). The supply chain is comprised of a supplier (green icon), two factories (orange icons), eight distribution centers (DC; red and purple icons), and 95 customers (blue icons) located across the globe (Fig. 1).

In the initial supply chain design, SCD_{global} , two producers in China (in Xiamen and Shenzhen) are supplied by a local supplier. The producers deliver the lighting equipment to the DCs in the United States, Paraguay, Belgium, Russia, India, China, South Africa, and Australia. From there, goods are shipped to the customers (e.g., retailers).

We consider two disruption scenarios, that is, a short-term production stop for one month and a long-term crisis of two years, using the example of the COVID-19 pandemic. Two possible network designs are examined: the initial one with a global footprint and a localized one when products are produced locally in the regions of sales (Figs. 2 and 3).

In the global network design, DCs in the right regions are shipped from two factories in China. In the localized design, factories are located in the regions of sales. We design our experimental environment to examine the role of localization for supply chain resilience under exposure to disruptions of different severities. The assessments are subject to the localization index (1) and two resilience indicators (OTF—Equation 2, and FR—Equation 3). OTD is used to measure the

Fig. 1. Supply chain design (screenshot from anyLogistix).

operational resilience perspective. It is the ratio of customer orders delivered on time to all orders placed by the customers (Equation 2).

$$OTD = \frac{\text{number of on - time orders}}{\text{total number of orders placed}} \quad (2)$$

An order is considered to be on time if it is delivered within the ELT (expected lead time, i.e., the time between when a customer places an order and receives it). The ELT service level has been used as a resilience indicator in a multitude of studies (Ivanov, 2020; Singh et al., 2021). We note that in anyLogistix, the ELT service level considers statistics related only to the order delivery phase. The actual order fulfilment time (i.e., the time between order generation and order delivery) can be longer due to a disruption causing waiting time (i.e., a backlog).

FR is used to measure customer's perspective of resilience. It is the ratio of orders successfully fulfilled from available inventory-on-hand to the total number of orders placed (Equation 3).

$$FR = \frac{\text{number of customer orders successfully fulfilled from available inventory - on - hand}}{\text{total number of orders placed}} \quad (3)$$

Our analysis is subject to answering the following questions:

1. What is the impact of localization on supply chain performance and resilience?
2. How are localization effects related to the disruption severity?
3. Are localization and globalization contradictory versus complementary strategies?

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Fig. 2. Global supply chain design.

3.3. Simulation model

In this section, we describe the supply chain control policies as applied in the model in line with Ivanov (2020) as shown in Fig. 4.

A discrete-event simulation model has been built in anyLogistix supply chain simulation and optimization software. anyLogistix allows for supply chain resilience modeling with the ability to create comprehensive simulation models, defining sourcing, inventory, production, and transportation control policies as well as performance indicators.

Visualization and analysis of structure, flow, and supply chain performance in dynamics is also possible. One drawback of using anyLogistix in research is its black-box nature and the limited number of pre-programmed control policies. However, these limitations can be addressed through integration and process customization in AnyLogic.

Fig. 3. Localized supply chain design.

The following major settings and assumptions have been included in the model. We consider deterministic demand to avoid operational vulnerability in the system, which might be over-crossed by disruption-driven variability. Customer orders are generated every seven days with varying order quantities at different customers (see Figs. 2 and 3). No extra risk mitigation inventory in the supply chain is considered. The lead time in the supply chain is subject to actual road distances and the defined speed of transportation means. The ELT for the customers is 30 days. Production and transportation capacity are unconstrained. Backordering is allowed. A simulation period of 365 days is considered.

The following logic has been used in the model in line with the study (Ivanov, 2020). The facilities have a risk mitigation inventory for a period between 15 and 30 days. The supply chain is characterized by partial visibility, that is, the demand of an upstream echelon is visible for the downstream echelon. The markets generate orders to the DC according to their demand, which is normally distributed (see Figs. 2 and 3). The DCs and producers exhibit the s, S inventory control policy and place the orders at the factory. Production is controlled by the parameters of inventory control policy. Factories also exhibit the s, S inventory control policy in line with (Boute et al., 2022). In particular, when deciding on the order quantity planning, the model checks the current inventory level, the re-order point, and the target inventory. This policy has been commonly used in literature about supply chain resilience analysis (Ivanov, 2025b). The policy parameters are shown in Appendix 1.

4. Experimental results and analysis

In this section, we first present experimental results. Subsequently, an analysis of their managerial implication is presented.

Fig. 4. Data model for simulation.

4.1. Experimental results

Our experiments begin with a nominal scenario (i.e., business as usual, disruption-free). This helps validate the correctness of the model and define benchmarks for scenarios with disruptions regarding “ideal” (i.e., disruption-free) performance. As expected, the OTD and FR in the disruption-free scenarios for both settings (i.e., global and local designs) are 100%. This is intuitive since no other vulnerabilities or uncertainties (e.g., demand and lead-time fluctuations) were considered in the modeling setting in the interest of clarity and to avoid any influence of other operational vulnerabilities.

Second, disruption scenarios are investigated. For both types of networks, two scenarios are simulated. In the first, short-term disruption scenario, factories in China are disrupted for one

Table 1
Localization index for nominal (disruption-free) scenario

Region	Regional sales, units	Sales from local manufacturing, units		Contribution to the LI (%)	
		$SCD_{initial}$	SCD_{local}	$SCD_{initial}$	SCD_{local}
South America	16,676.4	0	16,676.4	0	19.57
Europe	7992.4	0	7992.4	0	9.38
India	14,794.0	0	14,794.0	0	17.36
USA	5590.0	0	5590.0	0	6.56
Russia	5158.4	0	5158.4	0	6.05
China	30,638.4	30,638.4	30,638.4	100	36.67
South Africa	1934.4	0	1934.4	0	2.27
Australia	2423.2	0	2423.2	0	2.84
Total	83,542.9			100	100

Table 2
Localization and resilience indexes

Scenarios	Localization index	OTD, %	FR, %
Nominal (disruption-free)/ $SCD_{initial}$	36.67	100	100
Nominal (disruption-free)/ SCD_{local}	100	100	100
Short-term/ $SCD_{initial}$	36.67	95.2	85.1
Short-term/ SCD_{local}	100	99.1	98.4
Long-term/ $SCD_{initial}$	36.67	92.7	70.3
Long-term/ SCD_{local}	100	93.2	72.8

month beginning on April 15. In the long-term scenario, the COVID-19 pandemic case is replicated with the first disruption wave starting in China on January 25 and lasting 45 days, and the second wave in all other regions of the world starting on April 15 and lasting for 45 days. A warm-up period of 25 days has been used to ensure the stable work of the simulation model before a disruption. The model is terminated when it reaches a steady state, subject to a warm-up period and pre-disruption behaviour. A steady state is characterized by the values of OTD and FR indicators and stability of production-ordering-inventory dynamics for 100 days after the recovery from the last disruption in line with Ivanov (2025b).

Computational results for the localization ratio are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

It can be observed in Table 1 that in the initial design $SCD_{initial}$, when only China produces products, localization index is 36.67%, while in the SCD_{local} localization index is 100%. Our computational results suggest that localization impacts the supply chain resilience. A positive effect of localization can be observed in scenarios with short-term disruptions, and it decreases with an increase in shock duration and severity.

In the short-term disruption scenario, localization translates into higher OTD (99.1%, compared to 95.2%, in the initial network design with production in China only) and FR (98.4%, compared to 85.1%, in the initial network design with production in China only).

However, in the long-term, COVID pandemic-like crisis scenario, localization is less effective. Here, localization translates into a slight improvement of the OTD (93.2%, compared to 92.7%, in the initial network design with production in China only) and FR (72.8%, compared to 70.3%, in

Fig. 5. Resilience performance in the $SCD_{initial}$ scenario.

the initial network design with production in China only). While the improvements in resilience are marginal, localization might lead to higher costs (Aldrighetti et al., 2024; Lückner et al., 2024).

4.2. Managerial implications

Structural diversity, flexibility at the process and product levels, and identification of critical nodes and links are typically seen as main factors influencing resilience. We build on these observations when elaborating on managerial insights, which can be deduced from the experiments shown above.

The difference in the impact of localization on resilience in scenarios of different severity can be explained by several factors. First, inventory in our model ranges from 15 to 30 days of demand. This can be enough for a short-term disruption (up to 30 days). However, in case of longer disruptions, and even pandemic-like crises with several disruption waves, localization of production does not contribute to resilience because of the ripple effect (Dolgui et al., 2018; Habibi et al., 2025). Disrupted supply and lockdowns at factories and DCs lead to production stops in the regions translating into lower OTD and FR (Fig. 5).

Different colors in Fig. 5 depict five different products. The OTD and FR dynamics of all five products follow similar patterns. It can be observed that long-term disruption scenario results in a lower resilience measured both by the values of OTD and FR, and the recovery time.

In light of these observations, mixed strategies combining local and global footprints can be recommended to increase supply chain resilience. A mix of global and local supply increases system flexibility and variety. Therefore, we argue that localization and global sourcing can be supplementary strategies. Diversified sourcing and production flexibility allow the adaptation of the supply chain without additional investments and in a very short time. The primary advantage of localization in enhancing resilience is to reduce lead times and improve service levels by relocating suppliers and facilities closer to production and consumption points. Although the shift to localization raises costs, expanding the number of sites with safety stock can strengthen resilience.

5. Conclusion

Supply chain resilience is concerned with both establishing disruption-resistant operational practices and ensuring achievement of some planned performance in the presence of shocks. Thus, resilience is both a quality and a quantity (Ivanov, 2024a). The extant literature is rich in analyzing each of these two parts separately (Behzadi et al., 2020; Bier et al., 2020). However, the studies connecting quantity and quality perspectives are rare. We position our study in the context of debates about the impact of localization on supply chain resilience. We departed from some industrial practices that use a localization degree as a measure of resilience.

Two substantial contributions emerge from our study. First, we defined a localization index of manufacturing activities in the supply chain. Second, we tested two hypotheses using discrete-event simulation model in anyLogistix: (i) Does a localization ratio impact supply chain resilience, and (ii) Which role does the severity of shocks play in the impact of localization on supply chain resilience. Our findings suggest that localization impacts supply chain resilience. A positive effect of localization can be observed in scenarios with short-term disruptions, and it decreases with an increase in shock duration and severity. For long-term crises, localization may not always be the right resilience strategy. A mixed strategy combining local and global footprints can be recommended as a resilient supply chain strategy. Therefore, we argue that localization and global sourcing are supplementary strategies.

Limitations exist, as with any study. The proposed localization index might need some adjustments for different applications, as it depends on the supply chain and product complexity. It also depends on the specialization degree of suppliers and the fraction of the rare components (e.g., critical minerals). Localization index can be extended toward multiple echelons and considered as a compounding function of sales, manufacturing, Tier-1 sourcing, and Tier-2 sourcing. We considered localization index in units; it can be considered in dollars as well. Finally, we used standard functionality of anyLogistix software, which might be extended in the future by adding some customized elements from AnyLogic.

Future research in this area can have multiple extensions. Localization value for resilience depends on the type of risks and disruption scenarios considered. Localization might be helpful in case of short-term disruptions or long-term isolation of some regions from the rest of the world. For long-term crises such as climate change, localization is not the right resilience strategy.

Localization and global sourcing are, therefore, not a trade-off. They are supplementary strategies. Diversified sourcing and production flexibility enable the adaptation of the supply chain without additional investments and in a very short time. The main advantage of localization for enhancing resilience is to shorten lead times and boost service levels by relocating suppliers and facilities closer to production and consumption points. Although the shift to localization raises costs, expanding the number of sites that hold safety stock has strengthened resilience. In the future, other factors affecting local vs global decisions can be included in modeling, for example, tariffs and global trade policies (Ivanov and Dolgui, 2025).

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Appendix 1: Inventory control policy parameters used for computational experiments.

	Facility Filter	Product Filter	Policy Type Filter	Policy Parameters		Facility Filter	Product Filter	Policy Type Filter	Policy Parameters
11	DC Asunción	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=60, S=120, safety stock=371.375	32	DC Moscow	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=16, S=33, safety stock=82
12	DC Asunción	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=116, S=232, safety stock=279	33	DC Moscow	Large home ap...	Min-max policy...	s=4, S=7, safety stock=18
13	DC Asunción	Large home ap...	Min-max policy...	s=57, S=114, safety stock=297	34	DC Moscow	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=9, S=17, safety stock=163
14	DC Asunción	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=83, S=166, safety stock=318	35	DC Moscow	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=3, S=7, safety stock=17
15	DC Asunción	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=158, S=316, safety stock=281	36	DC Nanchang	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=54, S=107, safety stock=269
16	DC Brussels	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=13, S=25, safety stock=115	37	DC Nanchang	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=40, S=79, safety stock=200
17	DC Brussels	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=12, S=23, safety stock=93	38	DC Nanchang	Large home ap...	Min-max policy...	s=32, S=64, safety stock=162
18	DC Brussels	Large home ap...	Min-max policy...	s=21, S=41, safety stock=96.25	39	DC Nanchang	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=22, S=44, safety stock=110
19	DC Brussels	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=11, S=22, safety stock=116	40	DC Nanchang	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=35, S=71, safety stock=177
20	DC Brussels	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=9, S=18, safety stock=16	41	Factory Shenzh...	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=95, S=189, safety stock=33
21	DC Chandrapur	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=93, S=187, safety stock=75	42	Factory Shenzh...	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=137, S=273, safety stock=0
22	DC Chandrapur	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=123, S=245, safety stock=43	43	Factory Shenzh...	Large home ap...	Min-max policy...	s=95, S=189, safety stock=40
23	DC Chandrapur	Large home ap...	Min-max policy...	s=52, S=104, safety stock=42	44	Factory Shenzh...	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=109, S=217, safety stock=1
24	DC Chandrapur	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=155, S=311, safety stock=125	45	Factory Shenzh...	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=95, S=189, safety stock=7
25	DC Chandrapur	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=59, S=118, safety stock=53	46	Factory Xiamen	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=343, S=686, safety stock=0
26	DC Dallas	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=15, S=30, safety stock=51	47	Factory Xiamen	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=350, S=700, safety stock=117
27	DC Dallas	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=2, S=4, safety stock=35	48	Factory Xiamen	Large home ap...	Min-max policy...	s=284, S=567, safety stock=0
28	DC Dallas	Large home ap...	Min-max policy...	s=20, S=40, safety stock=104.5	49	Factory Xiamen	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=308, S=616, safety stock=0
29	DC Dallas	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=65, S=130, safety stock=125	50	Factory Xiamen	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=294, S=588, safety stock=56
30	DC Dallas	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=28, S=56, safety stock=111	51	Port Durban	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=14, S=28, safety stock=0
31	DC Moscow	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=3, S=6, safety stock=15	52	Port Durban	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=194, S=388, safety stock=39.5
					53	Port Durban	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=36, S=72, safety stock=0
					54	Port Durban	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=72, S=144, safety stock=80
					55	Port Sydney	Furniture	Min-max policy...	s=12, S=24, safety stock=12
					56	Port Sydney	Gardening equ...	Min-max policy...	s=22, S=44, safety stock=19
					57	Port Sydney	Large home ap...	Min-max policy...	s=42, S=84, safety stock=42
					58	Port Sydney	Lighting	Min-max policy...	s=19, S=38, safety stock=34
					59	Port Sydney	Small appliances	Min-max policy...	s=42, S=84, safety stock=54